

depending upon the amount incorporated in the soil. We studied N release from sesbania green manure and its effect on timing fertilizer N application.

Soil of the experiment was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with 5 mm percolation/h. It had pH 8.4, EC 0.15 mmho/cm, 0.34% organic carbon, 0.06% N, and 8 $\mu\text{g/g}$ KCl-extractable $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$. Finely chopped 2-mo-old fresh sesbania was mixed 20% by volume with soil with and without fertilizer N. The soil samples were submerged and incubated at $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Three samples from each treatment were taken at 4, 7, 14, 28, 42, and 56 d of incubation and extracted with 2 N KCl to determine $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content (Fig. 1).

In a field experiment, 2-mo-old sesbania, equivalent to 22 t green matter/ha and 120 kg N/ha, was incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice on 10 Jul 1984. All but the no-green-manure plots received the same amount of sesbania. At last puddling, 26-30 kg PK/ha was applied

to all plots. Urea N at 40-120 kg/ha was applied in different combinations at transplanting or 21 or 42 d after transplanting (DT). The crop was harvested at maturity and grain yield was determined at 14% moisture content.

The kinetics of KCl-extractable $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ indicated that sesbania began releasing N soon after incorporation. At 4 d of incubation, 44 and 23 mg $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N/kg}$ was received in soil with sesbania, with and without applied N. Peak $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ was within 7 to 14 d of sesbania incor-

poration and release remained steady through 56 d.

Data indicated that incorporating sesbania alone gave yield as high as applying 120 kg N/ha as urea (Fig. 2). Furthermore, with sesbania, applying 40-60 kg fertilizer N/ha at 42 DT gave yields at par with treatments where N was applied at transplanting or 21 DT. Sesbania-N was sufficient for rice at early growth stages. Topdressing 40 kg N/ha at 42 DT was necessary in lowland rice with incorporated sesbania. □

Effect of seeding rate and N levels on yield of direct-seeded rice

N. M. Chau, P. T. Hoang, B. K. Singh, and N. V. Luat, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute, Vietnam

We evaluated IR21717-42-1 performance at different seeding rates and N levels on a Ustifluent soil with pH 5.7 at Chau Thanh District, An Giang Province. N was applied at 40, 70, 100, or 130 kg/ha in

main plots and seeding rates were 200, 250, 300, 350, or 400 kg seed/ha in subplots. The experiment was in three replications. After land preparation, excess water was drained away and 13 kg P/ha as superphosphate was broadcast. Pregerminated seed was broadcast on uniformly puddled soil on 15 May 1983. N was applied, one-half at 20 d after sowing (DS) and in equal splits at 30 and 45 DS. Rice was harvested 18 Aug and yield was estimated from an 18-m² area.

Interaction between seeding rate and N level was significant. It was not possible to increase yield by increasing seeding rate beyond 200 kg/ha (see table). Data indicate that seeding rate might be reduced below 200 kg/ha without affecting yield. □

Grain yield as influenced by seed rate and N level, An Giang Province, Vietnam.

Seeding rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean
	40 kg N/ha	70 kg N/ha	100 kg N/ha	130 kg N/ha	
200	3.9	4.7	4.8	5.0	4.6
250	3.9	4.7	4.7	5.0	4.6
300	4.0	4.4	4.8	4.7	4.5
350	4.0	4.3	4.5	4.2	4.4
400	3.8	4.3	4.3	4.1	4.1
Mean	3.9	4.5	4.6	4.6	
<i>Main effects</i>		CD at 5%		CV (%)	
Seed rate (S)		0.2		6.7	
N level (N)		0.4		10.0	
<i>Interaction effects</i>					
Seed rate at a constant N level		0.3			
N at a constant S level		0.5			

Comparison of chemical indices for available K for rice in alluvial soils of Punjab

M. P. S. Gill and G. Dev, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India

We compared different soil tests for available K in 20 soils and their relationship to rice yield and K uptake in the greenhouse. Soils had pH 8.7 ± 0.4 , electrical conductivity 0.52 ± 0.26 mmho/cm, $0.44 \pm 0.18\%$ organic C, 57.4 ± 17.6 ppm $\text{KMnO}_4\text{-N}$, and 2.2 ± 1.1 ppm Olsen-P. Five 20-d-old PR106 seedlings grown in a K deficient solution were transplanted into pots each with 4.5 kg soil.

Treatments were 0 and 21 ppm K as KCl. A basal dose of 50 ppm N and 11 ppm P was applied to all pots and 50 ppm